

Studies in Phase Transfer Catalysis. Part-I. Permanganate Oxidation

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Oxidation of benzaldehyde, nitro chloro and methyl substituted benzaldehydes and benzyl cyanide by potassium permanganate under phase transfer catalytic conditions using different catalysts and solvents is reported. A correlation of structure-activity relationship of the catalysts is made and a comparison is made of the efficacies of the solvents used.

PHASE transfer catalysis (PTC) is one of the most attractive new techniques in organic synthesis¹⁻³.

Herriott and Picker⁴ reported the oxidation of several organic substrates by potassium permanganate under phase transfer catalytic conditions using tricaprilmethylammonium chloride with very good yields. Menger *et al.*⁵ obtained a high yield of piperonylic acid by the oxidation of piperonal using cetyltrimethylammonium bromide⁵. Weber and Shepherd⁶ reported the controlled oxidation of olefins to the corresponding *cis*-glycols in moderate yields by potassium permanganate in dichloroethane using benzyltriethylammonium chloride as catalyst. Sam and Simmons⁷ used dicyclohexyl-18-crown-6 to solubilise potassium permanganate in benzene and oxidise a number of organic substrates in good to excellent yield. The catalyst was used also to oxidise catechols in dichloromethane solution to orthoquinones².

The present paper reports the potassium permanganate oxidation of benzaldehyde, substituted benzaldehydes and benzyl cyanide using various quaternary ammonium salts as catalysts and employing different solvents.

Experimental

All chemicals of standard quality were used. All liquids were freshly distilled.

Oxidation of benzaldehyde :

Oxidation of benzaldehyde was conducted by a procedure similar to that followed by Herriot and Picker⁴. To benzaldehyde (4 g) dissolved in solvent (60 ml), appropriate quantity of the catalyst was dissolved. To it was added a solution of potassium permanganate (4.8 g in 100 ml of water) all at a time and the mixture was stirred on a water-bath at room temperature for a specified time. Then sodium bisulphite and 50% hydrochloric acid were added to it till the manganese dioxide dissolved and a colourless mixture was obtained. The organic solvent was separated. The aqueous solution was

extracted with the organic solvent and the solvent layer was washed with water (4×5 ml). The water extracts were combined and extracted with the organic solvent (10 ml) which was then washed with water (5 ml). The mixed organic solvent solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. It was distilled and the residue of benzoic acid was dissolved in methanol (5 ml) which was previously neutralised to phenolphthalein, then water (1 ml) and phenolphthalein solution (2 drops) were added and titrated with 1N sodium hydroxide. From the quantity of benzoic acid formed the percent conversion was calculated.

Firstly, oxidation under non-catalytic conditions was studied to find the effect of (i) time (15, 30, 45 and 60 min), (ii) stirrer speed (100–1000 rpm) and (iii) quantity of the oxidising agent potassium permanganate (20–100% excess). The results (Tables 1 and 2) revealed that three factors were

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF STIRRER SPEED ON NON-CATALYTIC OXIDATION OF BENZALDEHYDE TO BENZOIC ACID

Solvent : Benzene, KMnO_4 = 20% excess, Time = 30 min, Room temperature

Stirred speed rpm	Conversion %
125	44
250	62
500	70
1000	70

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TIME AND QUANTITY OF KMnO_4 NON-CATALYTIC OXIDATION OF BENZALDEHYDE TO BENZOIC ACID

Solvent : Benzene, Room temperature

Quantity of KMnO_4 % excess	Conversion (%) at different time (min)			
	15	30	45	60
20	65	70	70	70
50	75	75	75	75
100	78	78	78	78

TABLE 3—OXIDATION OF BENZALDEHYDE USING DIFFERENT SOLVENTS AND CATALYSTS*

Sl. no	Catalyst	Benzene		Chloroform		Methylene chloride		Ethyl acetate	
		Catalyst concn. mmol/mol	Conversion %						
1.	Tetrabutylammonium bromide	120	95	160	90	140	90	120	67
2.	Tricaprylmethylammonium chloride	200	100	140	95	160	92	160	70
3.	Benzyl dimethylhexadecylammonium chloride	220	90	160	89	200	91	180	76
4.	Triethylbenzylammonium chloride	160	87	180	88	160	90	160	83

*Catalyst concentration was mmol per mol of benzaldehyde ;
All reactions were conducted at room temperature ; Time was 15 min.

TABLE 4—OXIDATION OF SUBSTITUTED BENZALDEHYDES USING DIFFERENT CATALYSTS*

Sl. no.	Compound Benzaldehyde	Conversion non-catalytic %	Conversion catalyst TBAB %	Concn. of catalyst TBAB mmol/mol	Conversion catalytic TCMAC %	Concn. of catalyst TCMAC mmol/mol
1.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	53	88	120	92	120
2.	<i>m</i> Nitro	84	90	160	98	120
3.	<i>o</i> -Nitro	63	87	80	87	80
4.	<i>p</i> -Methyl	73	93	100	93	100
5.	<i>m</i> -Methyl	70	95	80	100	80
6.	<i>o</i> -Methyl	57	70	80	70	80
7.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	50	97	120	100	120
8.	<i>m</i> -Chloro	56	100	120	100	120
9.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	40	65	120	65	120

*TBAB=Tributylammonium bromide ; TCMAC=Tricaprylmethylammonium chloride.

effective in increasing the conversion. A maximum conversion of 78% was possible under non-catalytic conditions. Then the reaction was conducted under catalytic conditions. A preliminary study revealed that in catalytic oxidation (i) there was no increase in conversion after 15 min since that was the optimum conversion, (ii) conversion did not increase with the stirrer speed and (iii) increase of KMnO_4 beyond 20% did not increase the conversion. Then the oxidation was studied using tetrabutylammonium bromide, tricaprilmethylammonium chloride, benzyl dimethylhexadecylammonium chloride and triethylbenzylammonium chloride. The catalysts were employed in concentrations of 80–200 mmol per mol of benzaldehyde. The percentage conversion in 15 min at room temperature was estimated. Then the catalyst concentration giving the maximum conversion was employed and the reaction was conducted for 30, 45 and 60 min, each determination being a separate experiment. Four solvents were used, namely, benzene, chloroform, methylene chloride and ethyl acetate. The salient features of the results are summarised in Table 3. No increase in conversion was found beyond 15 min in any case as it was the maximum conversion observed. Experiments with cetyltrimethylammonium bromide and cetylpyridinium chloride could not be conducted due to emulsification.

Oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes : *p*-, *m*-, and *o*-nitro, methyl and chlorobenzaldehydes were similarly oxidised by aqueous neutral permanganate solution. Two catalysts, namely, tetrabutylammonium bromide and tricaprilmethylammonium chloride were employed and benzene was used as solvent.

A 40–60% excess of potassium permanganate brought out the maximum conversion in non-catalytic oxidation, while in catalytic oxidation 40% excess was enough. All reactions were conducted at room temperature. Maximum conversion took place in 30 min, and in catalytic system the reaction was completed in 15 min in most of the cases. The salient features of the findings are shown in Table 4.

Oxidation of benzyl cyanide : Oxidation of benzyl cyanide by neutral aqueous potassium permanganate was conducted similarly. Benzene was used as solvent. A uniform catalyst concentration of 180 mmol per mol of benzyl cyanide was employed since this catalyst concentration was found to give usually best result in the previous experiments. The salient findings are tabulated in Table 5.

Experiments with cetyltrimethylammonium bromide could not be completed due to emulsification.

TABLE 5—OXIDATION OF BENZYL CYANIDE USING DIFFERENT CATALYSTS IN DIFFERENT TIMES

Sl. no.	Catalyst	Conversion in 15 min %	Conversion in 30 min %
1.	Tetrabutylammonium bromide	41	42
2.	Tricaprylmethylammonium chloride	42	42
3.	Benzylidimethylhexadecylammonium chloride	40	40
4.	Triethylbenzylammonium chloride	16	16
5.	Cetylpyridinium chloride	25	25
6.	No catalyst	12	18

Results and Discussion

It is evident in all the systems studied that the catalytic activity is significantly present. Tetrabutylammonium bromide and tricaprilmethylammonium chloride functioned as better catalysts. Hence it can be concluded that bulky alkyl groups symmetrically disposed around the nitrogen usually make good catalysts. Tricaprylmethylammonium chloride was also found to be a very good catalyst since it carries bulky alkyl groups around though not absolutely symmetrical. Benzene was found to be the best solvent usually in most of the cases.

References

1. E. V. DEHMLOW and S. S. DEHMLOW, "Phase Transfer Catalysis", Springer-Verlag, Weinheim, 1980; C. M. STARKS and C. LIOTTA, "Phase Transfer Catalysis", Academic, New York, 1978.
2. W. P. WEBER and G. W. GOKEL, "Phase Transfer Catalysis in Organic Synthesis", Springer, Verlag, Berlin, 1977.
3. W. B. KELLER, "Compendium of Phase Transfer Reactions", Fluka, Buch, 1979; A. BRANDSTROM, "Preparative Ion Pair Extraction", Apotekar societeten, Stockholm, 1976; J. DOCKX, *Syntheses*, 1973, 441; G. W. GOKEL and W. P. WEBER, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1978, **55**, 350; W. P. WEBER and G. W. GOKEL, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1978, **55**, 429; M. MAKOSZA, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1975, **43**, 439; J. M. MCINTOSH, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1978, **55**, 235; J. M. LEHN, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1978, **11**, 49; E. V. DEHMLOW, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1977, **16**, 493; R. GALLO, H. DOU and P. HASSANALY, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1981, **90**, 849; E. CHIPELLINI, R. SOLARO and S. D'ANTONE, *Makromol. Chem.*, 1981, **82**; B. REUBEN and K. SJOBERG, *Chem. Tech.*, 1981, 315; E. V. DEHMLOW, *Chimia*, 1980, **34**, 12; L. LINDBLOM and M. ELANDER, *Pharm. Tech.*, 1980 59.
4. A. W. HERRIOT and D. PICKER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, 1511.
5. F. B. MENGER, J. U. REH and H. K. REH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1975, **40**, 3803.
6. W. P. WEBER and J. P. SHEPHERD, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1972, 4907.
7. D. J. SAM and H. E. SIMMONS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 4024.